

Deliverable 7.5: Second Impact Evaluation and Update to Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan

December 2025

Andria Nicodemou (BSC)
Lucy Martin (Met Office)
Grahame Madge (Met Office)
Davide Michielin (CMCC)
Rudi Bressa (CMCC)
Aleksandra Krzic (RHMZ)

Document information

D7.5: Second Impact Evaluation and Update to Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan	
Grant Agreement number	101081460
Project title	Adaptation-oriented Seamless Predictions of European Climate
Project acronym	ASPECT
Project start date	1 January 2023
Project duration	48 months
Work Package	WP7
Deliverable lead	Met Office
Author(s)	Andria Nicodemou (BSC) Lucy Martin (Met Office) Grahame Madge (Met Office) Davide Michielin (CMCC) Rudi Bressa (CMCC) Aleksandra Krzic (RHMZ)
Type of deliverable* (R, DEM, DEC, other)	R
Dissemination level** (PU, CO, CI)	PU
Date of first submission	30 December 2025
Revision n°	-
Revision date	-

Please cite this report as: Nicodemou, A., Martin, L., Madge, G., Michielin, D., Bressa, R., and Krzic, A. (2025). Plan D7.5 of the ASPECT project.

Disclaimer: *Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.*

* **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

** **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
About ASPECT.....	5
1 Introduction.....	6
1.1 Aim of the CDE plan	6
1.2 Definitions and aims of CDE.....	6
1.2.1 Communication.....	7
1.2.2 Dissemination	7
1.2.3 Exploitation	7
2 Target audiences	8
3 Activities, products and materials.....	9
3.1 Overview	9
3.2 Videos	13
3.3 Material.....	15
3.4 User engagement.....	17
3.5 Clustering / Collaborations	18
3.5.1 Interactions with other projects and initiatives.....	18
3.5.2 Interactions with RCOFs.....	20
3.6 Publications	23
3.7 Newsletters.....	23
3.8 Events and other activities.....	24
3.8.1 Conferences and events.....	24
3.8.2 Webinar series.....	25
4 Website.....	26
4.1 Layout.....	26
4.2 Analytics	28
5 Social media strategy	29
5.1 X (formerly Twitter) and Bluesky.....	29
5.1.1 Strategy	29
5.1.2 Analytics	30
5.2 LinkedIn.....	31
5.2.1 Strategy	31
5.2.2 Analytics	31
5.3 YouTube.....	31
5.3.1 Strategy	31
6 Visual identity	32
7 Exploitation	33
7.1 Digital handbook.....	34
7.2 The uptake of scientific advances.....	35
7.3 Supporting user training	35

7.4	Targeted engagement	35
8	Internal communication and interactions across the project	35
8.1	Mailing lists	35
8.2	Project wiki	36
8.2.1	Reporting and monitoring the impact of CDE activities	36
8.3	Meetings	36
9	Evaluation and risks	36
9.1	Impact evaluation and CDEP updates	36
9.2	Potential barriers and risks	37

List of figures

Figure 1.	ASPECT target audiences	9
Figure 2.	Frames from the introductory video	13
Figure 3.	Still images from the seamless climate predictions video	14
Figure 4.	Promotional video for ASPECT User Forum 2025.	14
Figure 5.	Still image from Ed Hawkins interview	15
Figure 6.	Paper Briefings, as shown on the website	15
Figure 7.	First page of infosheet on downscaling (left) and mid-project update (right), found in Resources > Infosheets.	16
Figure 8.	Poster providing an overview of the project, results and case studies. This was presented at the C3S General Assembly 2025.	17
Figure 9.	(Left) Partners from ASPECT and I4C in ECCA 2025, Rimini, Italy in June 2025. (Right) Agenda of first collaboration workshop with I4C in May 2025.	19
Figure 10.	(Top-left) ASPECT session at the Climateurope2 festival 2025 in Belgrade, Serbia. (Top-right) ASPECT coordinator Marta Terrado, with I4C partner Dragana Bojovic at Climateurope2 festival. (Bottom) ASPECT partners at Workshop on Climate Prediction and Services over the Atlantic-Arctic region" in Bergen, Norway in May 2024.	20
Figure 11.	Workshop leaflet and agenda.	21
Figure 12.	Promotion of the workshop on the X social media	22
Figure 13.	Total number of registered participants (left) and attendees (right).	22
Figure 14.	An excerpt from an ASPECT newsletter	23
Figure 15.	(Top) Agenda of first ASPECT webinar in December 2025. (Bottom) Part of the presentation by Veronica Torralba during the webinar.	26
Figure 16.	Part of the home page of ASPECT project, with brief information on the project and menus of different sections appearing in the top bar	27
Figure 17.	(Top) Progression of visitors to website. (Bottom) Map images showing the countries from which users have visited the ASPECT website. More than 80% of total visits were from European countries.	28
Figure 18.	A screenshot of the BlueSky and X posts with the highest engagement,	30
Figure 19.	Project logo, for both white and dark backgrounds	32
Figure 20.	Colour palette used in ASPECT.	32
Figure 21.	Two different screenshots of the beta version of the ASPECT handbook.	34

List of tables

Table 1.	Planned communication (C), dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and user engagement (UE) activities, including target audience, method/channel of communication and key performance indicator (KPI) targets for monitoring project impact.	10
Table 2.	Ongoing projects or initiatives relevant to ASPECT	18
Table 3.	Risks identified, related to CDE. High (H), Moderate (M) and Low (L) likelihood and severity are assigned to each risk.	37

Executive Summary

This document presents an update of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) for ASPECT. It outlines the planned and ongoing activities to maximise the reach and impact of the project's research and its achievements, as well as an evaluation of the impact of activities performed during the first 36 months of the project. The first version of this document (D7.1) was published in month 6, with a subsequent version in M18, and a final update expected in M47.

Among others, the CDEP outlines the aims of ongoing and planned CDE tasks, the main target audiences, the specific activities that will be carried out during the project's lifetime and the purpose of these activities, as well as the exploitation strategy. The communication channels, website, social media strategy, types of material and content, as well as other practical information, such as visual identity, are also detailed in this document.

About ASPECT

ASPECT aims to set up and demonstrate a seamless climate information (SCI) system with a time horizon up to 30 years and accompanied with underlying research and using climate information for sectoral applications. The project's goal is to improve existing climate prediction systems and to merge their outputs across timescales together with climate projections to unify a SCI as a standard for sectoral decision-making.

The project focus will be on European climate information, but we will also look where there is a wider policy interest (e.g., disaster preparedness) and in regions of European interest. We will maintain a strong link with the WCRP lighthouse activities to exploit learning for explaining and predicting earth system change. To provide a diversity of information, the SCI system will be based on multi-model climate forecasts and will build on learning from projects such as EUCP. It will align with new activities on Digital Twins within Europe, including DestinE. The SCI will combine physical science aspects with those from other disciplines to ensure the information is robust, reliable, and relevant for a range of user-driven decision cases. The information package will incorporate baseline forecasts and projections (plus uncertainty), and will explore new frontiers (e.g., extremes which are of socioeconomic high-level interest).

To ensure success, the research will encompass: an understanding and attribution of various processes along timescales (such as exploring signal-to-noise ratio) and their impact on predictability, new ways of initialisation of the prediction systems, merging predictions with projections, provision of regional SCI for Europe by downscaling (statistical methods, AI) and HighRes models (including convection-permitting models) and innovative post-processing methods enhancing the skill and robustness of the climate forecasts.

1 Introduction

ASPECT aims to improve the provision of seamless climate information for a time horizon of up to the next 30 years, particularly aimed at different sectors, to help improve climate resilience across Europe. The pioneering scientific developments in seasonal to decadal (S2D) forecasts are essential to develop such capabilities, while it is also crucial to ensure that this information is translated in a way that is useful, usable and accessible for stakeholders. The success of the research project not only depends on the results, but also on successful communication, dissemination and exploitation (CDE) to maximise the project reach and impact.

ASPECT is a user-oriented project, and thus effective CDE is crucial to reach and engage users of climate information throughout the project's lifetime. A successful CDE strategy will facilitate a pathway to impact, enabling a legacy for the critical research developed in ASPECT to support adaptation decision making in Europe.

CDE activities will also support user engagement in other WPs, in particular WP4 and WP5, facilitating knowledge exchange between ASPECT researchers and users with the aim to match user needs with project outcomes. Finally, exploitation activities will ensure the legacy of the project beyond its lifetime.

This deliverable outlines the aims of CDE actions, the main target audiences, the specific activities that are being carried out and are planned, including the purpose of these activities. The communication channels, website, social media strategy, types of material and content developed, as well as other practical information, such as visual identity, are also detailed in this document.

It should be noted that this deliverable is an update to Deliverable 7.1 and D7.2. The impact of the CDE activities is evaluated in this deliverable (D7.5) and in a final update expected in M47 (D7.6).

1.1 Aim of the CDE plan

This document focuses on the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities carried out in ASPECT. The key objectives of the CDEP are to:

- Raise awareness about the project and maximise its impact
- Disseminate the project results and new capabilities
- Reach and engage a wide range of audiences
- Facilitate engagement with the user communities (carried out in WP4 and WP5) through tailored, sector-specific material
- Exploit the project developments and capabilities
- Build synergies with other projects and initiatives to exchange knowledge

1.2 Definitions and aims of CDE

Communication, dissemination and exploitation have been defined below with the specific purpose of ASPECT in mind, which includes the overarching aims, timeline, audiences and style of activities.

1.2.1 Communication

The purpose of communication activities is to reach out to society, increasing the project visibility and demonstrating how the project advancements can contribute to tackle climate adaptation challenges. Communication activities aim to promote the project and build awareness about the activities and developments, from the start to the completion of ASPECT. It is important that carefully constructed key messages are communicated at a suitable time and using appropriate language for targeted audiences. Multiple and diverse target audiences have been identified, such as policymakers who are likely to require concise and non-technical communications, and climate researchers who will require specific and technical content. A number of communication tools and channels are used to inform these audiences, including (among others) the project website, social media, press releases, communication material (e.g., videos, infographics, sector-specific material), and news articles. A more detailed description of communication activities can be found in Table 1. Communication activities will be regularly monitored and evaluated to assess their impact.

1.2.2 Dissemination

The primary purpose of dissemination activities is to deliver relevant and tailored information on the outcomes of ASPECT to different target audiences, as well as to promote the project results and their uptake by different groups. Findings will be synthesised and shared to maximise the impact of the project, making sure they are available and accessible to those who can make best use of them. A host of different activities and materials will be prepared, including webinar series, case studies and paper briefings. All activities and outputs will be tailored to the specific target audience, overall aiming to be informative and clear, with the language and level of technical details appropriate to the target audience. The majority of dissemination activities will occur once results have been generated.

1.2.3 Exploitation

The purpose of exploitation is to enable the long-term impact and legacy of the developments and products that are generated by the ASPECT project. The exploitation activities aim to facilitate the use of ASPECT data, methods, and learnings in research and activities further to those covered by the project. Looking ahead to the final year of the project, exploitation is increasingly becoming the key priority, with recent engagement across work packages ensuring all consortium members are involved in detailed exploitation activity planning. Through all of the exploitation activities, we aim to create pathways to impact that will continue after the project concludes. The website, which includes all ASPECT data outputs, will remain open for four years after the project, ensuring continued access for users and researchers to use and build on ASPECT results. Section 7 of this report contains more detailed information about our exploitation plans.

2 Target audiences

ASPECT targets a range of different audiences with various levels of expertise in using climate information and different requirements summarised in Figure 1. Within these groups, the project will continue to interact with stakeholders in a range of key relevant socio-economic sectors, including the sectors of the ASPECT Super Users (i.e. agriculture, finance, governance, humanitarian and disaster relief). Each of these stakeholders are interested in information spanning different timescales (seasonal, decadal and longer term), as well as a wide range of spatial scales and regions. The main target audiences are identified below:

- **Climate research community**
We will continue to share developments in climate predictions with the scientific community to facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration with researchers, and relevant projects and initiatives. ASPECT champions (partners who are affiliated with other relevant projects such as Impetus4Change, Climateurope2, and World Climate Research Programme (WCRP)), are important links into the wider research community.
- **Decision makers in government, businesses and the third sector**
We engage with decision makers, often non-experts in climate information use, to improve their awareness of the climate risk information available and its potential applications.
- **Climate information aggregators and adaptation practitioners**
We will share project findings with climate service providers and other types of climate information aggregators to increase the awareness of ASPECT's research and enable the uptake of our learnings and data with organisations who work closely with end users. ASPECT champions provide important links into relevant organisations and projects in this space, such as the EU mission on climate adaptation.
- **Climate forecasters, including national meteorological services**
We will share advancements in data and methods with the climate forecasters and services communities. Sharing this learning enables exploration of potential new forecast products which national meteorological services could provide to their users and stakeholders to inform adaptation across a range of sectors in Europe.
- **General interest groups and wider society**
We will engage with non-experts and the wider public interested in climate information to enhance the reach of the project, raise awareness about climate information and promote the future uptake and use of this information by wider audiences.

Figure 1. ASPECT target audiences

3 Activities, products and materials

3.1 Overview

A comprehensive list of CDE activities that have been planned, carried out or underway are outlined in Table 1. Some of the activities have multiple and overlapping audiences or could fall into numerous categories (C, D, E or user engagement); for simplicity, the most important of these are noted in the table below. This plan of activities is adapted and evolves according to the project needs. Sections 3.2-3.8 provide more details on specific activities and material. Any revisions will be included in this update and the final CDEP update (D7.6 in M47). CDE material is available in English, while versions in other languages will be prepared if needed, prioritising those materials aimed to support user engagement activities.

Table 1. Planned communication (C), dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and user engagement (UE) activities, including target audience, method/channel of communication and key performance indicator (KPI) targets for monitoring project impact.

Activity	Type	Description and purpose	Target audience	KPI target	Due date (if relevant)	Status / Comments (updates until M36, December 2025)
Project website	C	The main communication hub for the project, aimed at those involved or interested in the project. It will provide the project description, latest news, events, reports, public deliverables, publications, and all communication material. A 'legacy' version of the website will be available for 5 years beyond the project end.	All	>500 visits over the lifetime of the project ⇒ <i>KPI achieved</i>	M48	Ongoing Website: www.aspect-project.eu/ Total visits: >2,900
News articles on project website	C	Short news articles about ASPECT advances, activities and events written in accessible language with a focus on societal benefits	All	>6 articles per year ⇒ <i>KPI achieved</i>	M48	Ongoing 11 articles in 2023, 6 articles in 2024, 9 articles in 2025 in the "News" section + 12 event entries in the "Events" section
Social media	C	Regular posts on social media will be made to reach a wider community, increase the project visibility and engage stakeholders.	All	>600 followers in total, >200 interactions ⇒ <i>KPI achieved</i>	M48	Ongoing Twitter : 227 followers, >45,400 impressions LinkedIn : 551 followers, >27,250 impressions Bluesky : 93 followers, 82 engagements Youtube : 13 subscribers, 637 views
Newsletters	C	Newsletters will be prepared and sent, with the frequency depending on the availability of project updates. The content will include upcoming events, key research highlights and opportunities for collaboration. Subscription to the newsletter has been promoted through the project website.	All, in particular ASPECT partners, Super Users, ASPECT community of practice, and relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives	~2 per year depending on content, >50 subscribers to the newsletter ⇒ <i>KPI achieved</i>		Ongoing 10 emails sent so far 371 subscribers
Press releases/briefings	C/D	Press releases and briefing materials will generate interest in the project, communicate about events and disseminate the results at local, regional and EU level. Disseminated on the project website, through social media and communication units of partners' organisations. The timing of press releases will aim to maximise impact.	Media, general public, all	≥3 press releases	M48	Ongoing Two articles / press releases published to date
Videos	C/D	Short videos to raise awareness and inform about key concepts and research conducted in the project to reach diverse audiences through social media and to be used in presentations.	All	≥6 short videos, >200 total views	M6-M48	Ongoing Two video so far, one under development
Policy briefs	C/D	Aim to co-produce targeted two-page briefs that synthesise and translate information on a specific subject of particular relevance to decision and	Policymakers, adaptation practitioners, other projects and initiatives	≥4 policy briefs		Future plans

		<p>policy makers. The specific subject matter of each brief will be chosen to maximise the dissemination of key messages that are policy relevant. The briefs will be disseminated through the project communication channels and at relevant events.</p>				
Clustering activities	C/D	<p>Collaborating and building synergies with relevant EU-funded projects, initiatives and clusters, including sister projects funded under the same call and other initiatives with partners' involvement (e.g., CORDEX, DestinE, EU Missions, Climateurope2)</p>	Relevant project and initiatives	<p>>5 collaborations ⇒ <i>KPI achieved</i></p>		<p>Ongoing Interacted with >15 relevant projects and initiatives, e.g. joined events (see section 3.5)</p>
Infographics	C/D	<p>Visually striking and concise representation of key messages/findings from the project for specific audiences with the possibility to be integrated in other dissemination materials such as policy briefs, news articles and the ASPECT digital handbook.</p>	All	<p>>4 infographics, with >100 total engagements with infographics on social media</p>		<p>Ongoing 1 infographic so far</p>
Sector-specific dissemination material	C/D	<p>Material tailored to the different sectors of interest of the project developed to facilitate engagement with users and present the application of the project's outcomes to a wider community (e.g. leaflet, poster). Disseminated through the project website and used in the multi-sector user forums.</p>	Adaptation practitioners, non-scientist decision-makers	<p>>100 views >3 sectors targeted</p>		<p>Ongoing 5 posters so far</p>
Webinar series	C/D	<p>Webinars targeting the different sectors tackled in the project, aimed to promote online discussions among participants (e.g., on scaling up project prototypes) and build capacity. Webinar recordings available on the project website.</p>	Adaptation practitioners, non-scientist decision makers and advisors, operational forecasters and climate service providers, early career scientists and students	<p>>300 total attendees</p>		<p>Ongoing 1 webinar so far, 38 attendees</p>
Scientific publications	D	<p>Sharing public project reports and publications in peer-reviewed journals will disseminate key project findings to the scientific community and climate adaptation community</p>	Climate research community, adaptation practitioners, operational forecasters and climate service providers	<p>>10 publications ⇒ <i>KPI achieved</i></p>		<p>Ongoing 35 peer-reviewed journal publications to date, more submitted or awaiting publication</p>
Paper briefings	D	<p>Digested briefings of specific ASPECT papers and their implications will be disseminated through the project communication channels to ensure the key messages from the research also reach non-technical audiences.</p>	Academia (beyond climate science community), adaptation practitioners, non-expert decision-makers	<p>>10 paper briefings (*see note)</p>		<p>Ongoing 4 paper briefing done</p>
ASPECT Shorts	C/D	<p>Short infosheets on concepts behind ASPECT research and results.</p>	All audiences	<p>>5 shorts</p>	M48	<p>Ongoing 1 short and 1 mid-project update</p>
Participation in relevant events	D	<p>Presentations in relevant events that can help engaging with interested audiences while increasing the reach of project results, e.g., European Geophysical Union (EGU), European Meteorological Society (EMS), European Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA)</p>	Research community, adaptation practitioners, relevant EU-funded initiatives	<p>>10 conference/workshop presentations ⇒ <i>KPI achieved</i></p>		<p>Ongoing Participation in >45 conferences and relevant events (more information in Section 3.8)</p>

Case study booklet	D	Appealing document describing the co-production process followed for the development of the case studies and their application. Disseminated through the project communication channels.	Academia, adaptation practitioners, climate service providers	>100 views, >50 interactions	M42	Future plans
Digital Handbook	C/D/E	A digital environment available through the project website to support stakeholders in applying and navigating the results of the project in diverse socio-economic sectors and contexts.	Non-technical decision makers, adaptation practitioners	>200 views and interactions	Beta version by M36	Ongoing
User training events (in collaboration with WP5) (**see note)	D/E	Support a user training event, organised in collaboration with WP5 and other WPs, to train new and existing users of climate predictions on the use of the delivery system developed in the project, building on foundations of the webinar series delivered earlier in the project.	Adaptation practitioners, non-technical decision makers, national meteorological services, climate service providers	>25 participants	M42	Future plans
Case studies	D/UE	Case studies co-developed with superusers from different socio-economic sectors to co-explore how different types of climate-related information (e.g. climate variables, indicators, risk indices, etc.) at various time-scales can help inform decisions for adaptation to climate change.	Super Users, adaptation practitioners, climate service providers	Support 5 case studies	M42	Ongoing (WP4) Supporting the needs of case studies
Engagement with national meteorological services	E	Support engagement with national meteorological services. Activities will include 1-2-1 consultations to understand their needs and challenges, involvement of the meteorological services in the design of the ASPECT delivery system, and tailored engagement to support and monitor the meteorological services as they begin to incorporate the new information and approaches into their own workflows, products and services.	National meteorological services	≥5 national met services engaged <i>⇒ KPI achieved</i>	M48	Ongoing Dedicated workshop and other engagement
Multi-sector user forums	D/UE	Support annual multi-sector user forums to create a physical, virtual or hybrid space of interaction between ASPECT scientists and users of climate information	Adaptation practitioners, non-technical decision makers and advisors	>200 participants in total <i>⇒ KPI achieved</i>	M48	First user forum in two parts (Mar and Apr 2023); Second User Forum (Feb 2024) Total: >260 participants

*Note: The KPI for paper briefings has been amended compared to that originally mentioned in the proposal (reduced from >25 to >10) to reflect recent feedback and learning from other projects, which found that there was limited engagement from our target audience with paper briefings. We are, therefore, focusing our efforts on materials that we anticipate will be more of interest to our target audiences, such as the ASPECT Shorts, which is a new activity aiming to produce at least 5 brief infosheets to explain ASPECT concepts and results.

**Note: Apart from the user training event, WP7 is supporting activities organised by other WPs, such as the User Forums. These are marked without bold in the table above.

More details on specific activities are provided in subsequent sections.

3.2 Videos

Short bespoke videos will raise awareness for the ASPECT project, communicate key concepts and share research highlights. A video introducing the project has recently been published, and as well as a further video explaining the concept of seamless climate predictions. Further videos are currently under development. The videos are shared widely on all project social media channels, and are embedded on the project website under the Resources > [Resource library](#) section.

3.2.1 Introductory video

The first video focuses on introducing the project and can be found on [Youtube](#) and the project website. A storyboard of images from the introductory video is shown in Figure 2. The video content covers:

- An introduction to ASPECT project aims and the context of the existing research landscape
- The user-centred approach used in ASPECT
- The expected benefits from ASPECT research

Figure 2. Frames from the introductory video

3.2.2 Seamless climate prediction explainer video

A video explaining seamless climate predictions has also been prepared. The aim of the video is to explain this concept and show how ASPECT will further our understanding in this area, using the concept of a camera and capturing a landscape. The video is also available on [Youtube](#). Some images from the video are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Still images from the seamless climate predictions [video](#).

3.2.3 Plans for future videos and other audiovisual content

During the latest ASPECT general assembly held in Bologna, Italy, a number of video interviews of project researchers, as well as some attendees to the local User Forum, were recorded. Using a blend of these recorded interviews, combined with new content, we are preparing a video examining the challenges of extreme weather and climate change impacts. This will focus on how the ASPECT project supports adaption. Interviewees will include scientists and key figures from the ASPECT project, as well as external interviewees.

Other videos are also created as needed, for social media and other purposes. For instance, footage from an interview with Suraje Dessai (University of Leeds; ASPECT WP5) was used for a promotional video about the annual User Forum 2025, also available on [Youtube](#).

Figure 4. Promotional video for ASPECT User Forum 2025.

Additionally, the ASPECT team had the opportunity to record a recent interview with eminent climate scientist Professor Ed Hawkins, available in the project’s Youtube channel.

Figure 5. Still image from Ed Hawkins interview.

Finally, a video resulting from a collaboration with the DestinE initiative is currently under preparation, which shows how the Digital Twin for Climate Change Adaptation can provide information tailored to users from the viticulture sector. Although the video focuses on the Digital Twin technology, the indicators shown have been identified in the user research phase of ASPECT.

3.3 Material

Paper briefings are prepared for high-impact publications, or those with a wider policy or sectoral interest. The paper briefings are written in an accessible way to maximise the audience reach. The briefings will take the following structure:

- Introduction
- Context, which provides background information to help the reader understand the novelty or significance of the new research
- A summary of the key findings from the paper
- implications of the research

The paper briefings that have been produced so far are available on the relevant section of the ASPECT website: [Paper Briefings - Aspect](#)

Figure 6. Paper Briefings, as shown on the website.

Other material developed and planned in the project include **infosheets**, also called *ASPECT Shorts* in the project, which provide background information on concepts behind the project research. These can be found under the [Resources > Infosheets](#) section of the website.

The first infosheet focused on the topic of “[Downscaling of climate predictions](#)”. This 3-page document provided an overview of what downscaling is and the different approaches used, how downscaled information is useful for users, and what has been done in ASPECT so far. There are plans for further infosheets on other relevant topics, such as temporal merging.

In addition, an overview of the first two years of the project was developed in early 2025, called the “[ASPECT Mid-Project Update](#)”. This 14-page document gives an introduction to the project, its objectives, key concepts like seamless predictions and its user-centred approach, while describing the research conducted so far in each WP and key findings.

Figure 7. First page of infosheet on downscaling (left) and mid-project update (right), found in Resources > Infosheets.

Furthermore, we have prepared **five posters** so far, for instance, a poster providing an overview of the ASPECT project and introduction to seamless predictions, as well as one giving an overview of the results of the WP5 survey on climate information use. These posters were presented at several events (e.g. C3S General Assembly 2024 and 2025), and will be used in future activities, as needed. These can be found in the [Resource Library](#) section of the project website.

Figure 8. Poster providing an overview of the project, results and case studies. This was presented at the C3S General Assembly 2025.

3.4 User engagement

User engagement (leading to the coproduction of climate information and services) is a core foundation of the project. User engagement activities are led by WPs 4 and 5. WP7 has contributed to user engagement activities by supporting the organisation of User Forums, assisting in the preparation of appropriate materials to engage users, alongside providing dedicated resources for communication activities. For more information on the User Forums, please refer to the Report on the annual multi-sector user forum (Deliverable 5.2).

ASPECT partners will provide training to the users of the research developed in ASPECT, with support from WP7; the target audiences will be national meteorological services, decision makers, and adaptation practitioners. The training will aim to allow the (potential) users of climate information to understand how the seasonal to decadal forecasts have been produced, how to use the delivery system produced in the project, and how to apply the new information appropriately. The training offer and level will be tailored to the user requirements and level, based on user engagement work, which is currently underway, led by WP5.

Besides these interactions, ASPECT is also exploring ways of engaging with different levels of potential users and purveyors of climate information, in particular those who have expressed interest in becoming Super Users, thus building a “community of practice”.

3.5 Clustering / Collaborations

3.5.1 Interactions with other projects and initiatives

The ASPECT project builds on previous knowledge, and aims to collaborate, share knowledge and exploit synergies with a range of existing national, European and international initiatives and projects, such as (but not limited to) those listed in Table 2. Scientific collaboration with new projects and programmes (such as WCRP Lighthouse activities and Destination Earth) are sought out. In particular, ASPECT has been engaging with sister projects (e.g. Impetus4Change), as well as other EU projects (e.g. Climateurope2 and nextGEMS). This allows the project to reach a wider group of stakeholders.

To aid scientific collaboration, and to enhance the cooperation and leadership, a number of named “ASPECT collaboration champions” have been appointed from other WPs across the project, who are already engaged in ongoing large-scale initiatives of interest to ASPECT. Several meetings have been held with the champions to identify and initiate possibilities for collaboration with these initiatives, and help knowledge interchange between the project and the initiatives. Potential suggestions include joint sessions to share lessons learned and identify results of potential interest to both sides. The role of the champions in serving as representatives for the project will become more active as important and relevant results become available.

Table 2. Ongoing projects or initiatives relevant to ASPECT.

Relevant ongoing project / initiative	Brief description
Climateurope2	Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services of greater value to society, which will provide trustworthy, user-relevant and usable information.
Destination Earth (DestinE)	Destination Earth (DestinE) is an initiative to develop a highly accurate digital model of the Earth on a global scale.
EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change projects, such as CLIMAAX , Mission Implementation Platform for Adaptation to Climate Change and Regions4Climate	The Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change focuses on supporting EU regions, cities and local authorities in their efforts to build resilience against the impacts of climate change.
Impetus4Change	Impetus4Change is improving near-term climate predictions for social transformation in regions and cities in Europe.
Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems (NextGEMS)	NextGEMS is building prototypes for a new generation of Earth system models to advance science, guide policy, and inform applications to support sustainable management of our planet.
World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) Lighthouse activities	The World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) has transdisciplinary lighthouse activities covering a range of topics the most relevant to ASPECT are: Digital Earths; and Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change
World Meteorological Organisation Global Annual to Decadal Climate Update (GADCU)	The GADCU is published annually (in May) and summarises the predicted future of the global climate over the next year and the next five years based on an ensemble of four global climate model predictions.

In particular, we have collaborated with our sister project Impetus4Change (I4C) in several occasions, including

- Participation in I4C kick-off meeting, presenting ASPECT
- Joint meeting between ASPECT and I4C to define synergies with DestinE

- European Meteorological Society 2024 joint session on “Setting, crossing, and transforming scales”
- Two joint online collaboration workshops in May 2025, bringing together researchers from the two projects (see second part of News article [here](#))
 - Workshop 1 focused on Downscaling
 - Workshop 2 focused on Climate Services Upscaling
- European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA) 2025 joint session on “Knowledge Integration for Climate Services: The Role of Knowledge Brokers” in Rimini, Italy (see News article [here](#))

Figure 9. (Left) Partners from ASPECT and I4C in ECCA 2025, Rimini, Italy in June 2025. (Right) Agenda of first collaboration workshop with I4C in May 2025.

Some of the interactions with other projects and initiatives are also below, while further are described in other relevant sections of this document (see detailed event information in “Other activities”):

- Participation in EERIE project’s kick-off meeting, presenting ASPECT
- Internal presentations and interactions with WCRP Lighthouse activity on the topic "External forcing of the North Atlantic Oscillation".
- ECCA 2023 joint session with Climateurope2 and TRUST project
- Participation in Climateurope2 festival 2024 (see News article [here](#))
- Joint organisation of “Workshop on Climate Prediction and Services over the Atlantic-Arctic region” in Bergen, Norway in May 2024, together with I4C, Climate Futures, CoRea and Roadmap Oceans (see News article [here](#))
- ECCA 2025 participation at MIP4Adapt session: “Upscaling climate services: sharing approaches and insights”
- ASPECT World Cafe session at Climateurope2 festival 2025 (see News article [here](#))
- Participation in LIFE CLIMAX PO project meeting / River Basin conference
- Presentation of ASPECT at MEDUSSE project’s General Assembly
- Joint organisation of Workshop on Understanding and Predicting Annual to Multi-Decadal Climate Variations (UPCLIV) in Bologna, Italy in November 2025 together with EXPECT, I4C, WCRP ESMO and EPESC.

Figure 10. (Top-left) ASPECT session at the Climateurope2 festival 2025 in Belgrade, Serbia. (Top-right) ASPECT coordinator Marta Terrado, with I4C partner Dragana Bojovic at Climateurope2 festival. (Bottom) ASPECT partners at Workshop on Climate Prediction and Services over the Atlantic-Arctic region" in Bergen, Norway in May 2024.

3.5.2 Interactions with RCOFs

Since the early stages of the project, ASPECT has been working on building relationships with national meteorological centres, Regional Climate Outlook Forums (RCOFs) and other similar communities, as several project partners are actively involved in these networks, such as the Republic Hydrometeorological Service of Serbia (RHMZ).

RCOFs, initiated by the World Meteorological Organization, bring together national, regional and international climate experts with the aim to provide consensus-based climate prediction for the upcoming season of summer or winter. RCOFs have spread to many regions across the world. In Europe, there are two RCOFs: the South East European Climate Outlook Forum (SEECOF) and the Mediterranean Climate Outlook Forum (MedCOF). MedCOF integrates already existing COFs in the region, PRESANORD (RCOF for North Africa) and SEECOF, and additionally integrates Western European and Middle Eastern Mediterranean countries. The core concept of all the RCOFs is delivering consensus-based climate outlook products to end users. The products are tailored to meet the local conditions and disseminated by each National Meteorological and Hydrological Service (NMHS).

Besides RCOFs, ASPECT has also established communication with the EUMETNET network of European NMHS, more specifically with the EUMETNET Climate, Numerical Weather Prediction and Climate Scenarios expert teams.

EUMETNET was created as an association with a primary mission to help cooperation and collaboration among its members and to represent them externally on a collective basis, particularly when communicating with European organisations, especially the EU and EC. The

focus of cooperation between members has been on the core capabilities of the members, in particular: observing systems, data processing, basic forecasting products, research and development, training, coordination of technical assistance, and production of essential output information to end-users, especially the citizens of Europe.

At the beginning of the ASPECT project, participants of the SEECOF, MedCOF and EUMETNET Climate expert team were informed about the project, and later invited to participate in User Forums and Workshops organized by the project. Since the activities in the SEECOF are conducted online in the form of a forum, a separate section was created in order to inform participants on the objectives of the project. Sharing information on the project activities and results with these communities will continue throughout the project.

On 22-23 October 2024, RHMZ with the help of other partners organised a two-day online workshop for national meteorological services (NMSs) titled “From Seasons to Decades: Seamless Prediction for a Better Future” (see more information in the News article [here](#)). The workshop focused on seasonal-to-decadal predictions, predictability research, and user needs. The event gathered representatives from national meteorological services based in Europe, Middle East and Africa, as well as from RCOFs operating in Europe region and beyond (SEECOF, MedCOF, NEACOF, PRESANORD), and from WMO and regional climate centers.

The figure shows two pages of a workshop leaflet and agenda. The left page is the leaflet, titled '22 and 23 October 2024 13:30-16:00 CEST, online' and 'Workshop for National Meteorological Services'. The main title is 'FROM SEASONS TO DECADES: SEAMLESS PREDICTION FOR A BETTER FUTURE'. The text describes the workshop's focus on showcasing cutting-edge climate forecasts and exploring new forecasting horizons. It mentions that ASPECT is a Horizon Europe project investigating seamless climate predictions. The workshop will explore new forecasting horizons and emphasize the added value of initialization in climate predictions. It will also discuss the limitations of state-of-the-art multi-system predictions. The agenda is divided into two days: Day 1 (22 October) and Day 2 (23 October). Day 1 includes a welcome, introduction, session 1 on seasonal to decadal predictions, current and future climate prediction systems at DWD, coffee break, novel configurations of prediction systems for seamless climate information, ASPECT data management guidelines, and a roundtable & discussion. Day 2 includes a welcome, session 2 on predictability & novel approaches, opportunities and challenges of seasonal-to-decadal climate predictions, what can novel approaches towards seamless climate information further add to climate services?, roundtable & discussion, coffee break, session 3 on user needs, co-development of case studies with Super Users, climate information use in Europe, and a final roundtable & discussion. The right page is the agenda, titled '22 and 23 October 2024 13:30-16:00 CEST, online' and 'ASPECT'. It lists the schedule for both days, including times and topics for each session, such as 'Welcome & Introduction to workshop', 'Session 1: Seasonal to Decadal predictions', 'Current and future climate prediction systems at DWD', 'ASPECT data management: guidelines and documentation', 'Roundtable & Discussion', and 'Wrap-up'.

Figure 11. Workshop leaflet and agenda.

The workshop was promoted on the ASPECT social media, newsletter and website. Since the workshop was dedicated to NMSs and participation was by invitation only, the event promotions included an email for interested parties to express their interest. The call on X platform was posted several times with a maximum number of 106 views. The call for participation was mainly distributed through different networks of NMSs, as well as with the project partners' contacts.

More than 235 persons were contacted directly, and six networks further disseminated the call to their members.

Figure 12. Promotion of the workshop on the X social media.

In total, 149 people from 40 countries participated in the event (including project partners), while 62 participants from NMSs attended the workshop on both days. There was a total of 179 registered participants from 44 different countries, of which 146 were participants from NMSs. The countries with the most representation were the UK (16), Azerbaijan (12), Romania (8) and Serbia (8), when excluding project partners.

Figure 13. Total number of registered participants (left) and attendees (right).

Positive feedback on the Workshop for NMSs was shared by its speakers and panellists during the WMO RA VI RCC User Forum and RA VI RCC Coordination Team meeting, held in November 2024. The need for decadal predictions, as expressed by NMSs, was emphasized, highlighting the importance of the ASPECT project in providing valuable information.

Additionally, the mailing list was expanded by ~75 contacts from those who expressed interest in being informed about ASPECT activities.

More information on the Workshop can be found in “MS26: Review of participation in RCOF events and engagement with National Met Services, summarise progress to date and ongoing strategy”.

3.6 Publications

There have been 35 peer-reviewed journal articles published from ASPECT to date, as well as several posters. Currently, more than 10 papers are in the submission stage. All ASPECT-funded papers are available on the project website under the “[Resources > Journal papers](#)” section, and are promoted through the project channels.

3.7 Newsletters

The project has built a community of over 371 people who are subscribed to the project’s mailing list. Periodic newsletters are sent to these subscribers, as well as emails inviting them to the User Forums or sharing other project related information.

To date, 7 newsletters have been shared, which included information on the latest project news, including high profile research outcomes, publications and upcoming events of interest, and an additional 3 emails promoting specific events (user forums and webinar). An excerpt of a newsletter is shown in Figure 5 below. Forthcoming newsletters will continue to share the latest highlights from ASPECT in an accessible and engaging way.

Figure 14. An excerpt from an ASPECT newsletter.

3.8 Events and other activities

3.8.1 Conferences and events

Besides the aforementioned activities, ASPECT partners have participated in a large number of events and scientific conferences (more than 45 events so far), engaging with the scientific community, general public and other project audiences, thus bringing visibility to the project and results. A non-comprehensive list showing some of the events in which ASPECT partners have participated can be found below:

- **Climateurope2 webstival** (March 2023) - Actively involvement and holding the first User forum at the webstival, titled "Adaptation-oriented seamless predictions of European climate"
- **Oxford Climate Research Network - Annual Event** (May 2023 and March 2024) - Poster presentation on ASPECT project at the event
- **6th European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA) 2023** (June 2023) - Co-hosting session on "Communities of Practice: Engagement Strategies", together with Climateurope2 and TRUST projects
- **Business Travel Association Planet Plan Conference** (July 2023) - Introductory presentation on weather and climate risk to transport sector including brief overview of ASPECT and Super User Competition
- **C3S General Assembly** (Sept 2023, June 2024 and June 2025) - Several posters presented by ASPECT partners
- **UK Regulators Network Young Professionals Conference event** (Sept 2023) - introductory presentation on weather and climate risk to transport sector including brief overview of ASPECT and Super User Competition
- **Climateurope2 Festival** (March 2024) - Keynote talk on survey findings, pitch presentation and interactive round table of ASPECT concepts (info [here](#))
- **EGU 2024** (April 2024) - Presentation of several posters (info [here](#))
- **NCAR Workshop on Predictability across time scales** (April 2024) - Presentation by ASPECT partners
- **River Basin conference (CLIMAX-PO)** (April 2024) - Participation of ASPECT partners
- **Workshop on Climate Prediction and Services over the Atlantic-Arctic region** (May 2024) - ASPECT participating in organisation of the workshop in Bergen, Norway, together with Impetus4Change, Climate Futures, CoRea, and Roadmap Oceans. There was a large number of presentations and sessions from partners (info [here](#))
- **Local event on climate change and drought in Catalonia** (May 2024) - Participation in roundtable together with Lobelia Earth (specialised in Earth Observation to address the climate emergency).
- **IMSC2024 - 15th International Meeting on Statistical Climatology** (June 2024) - Presentation by ASPECT partners
- **RMetSoc conference** (July 2024) - Participation in workshop and panel
- **EMS - European Meteorological Society** conference (Sept 2024 and Sept 2025) - joint session with I4C on on "Setting, crossing, and transforming scales" in 2024, several presentations and posters in both years
- **Campus Gutenberg**, Barcelona (Sept 2024) - Presentation of poster with ASPECT research and indicators relevant to droughts
- **WGNE39 + WGNE/WGSIP Joint Meeting**, Toulouse (Nov 2024) - Presentation of ASPECT

- **NOAA CPO Earth System Science and Modelling Advisory Council**, USA (Nov 2024) - Presentation about ASPECT
- **UNCCD COP16 Meeting**, Saudi Arabia (Dec 2024) - Presentation on seamless climate information for climate extremes
- **'Building Resilience to Extreme Heat: Health, Energy, Sustainability & Governance' workshop**, Oxford (Feb 2025) - Presentation of ASPECT and British Red Cross case
- **WCRP-CLIVAR-Wirtky Symposium**, Honolulu (March 2025) - Presentation of efforts on 2-year integrations
- **ECMWF AS2025 Annual Seminar**, Bonn (Apr 2025) - Posters and presentations
- **RA VI RCC Network Workshop** "Advancing Regional Climate Services to Meet Evolving Needs of RA VI Members" (Apr 2025) - Participation of ASPECT partners
- **European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA) 2025** conference, Rimini, Italy (June 2025) - Joint workshop with I4C and participation in MIP4Adapt session
- **MEDUSSE** Cost Action event (June 2025) - Presentation of ASPECT
- **Exeter Climate Forum** (July 2025) - Talk and poster presentation
- **Climateurope2 festival**, Belgrade (Sept 2025) - World Cafe session and participation in other sessions
- **IEA Wind Task 51 Workshop on Forecasting Extremes in the Power System** (Oct 2025) - participation / presentations of ASPECT partners

Other activities include the publication of [press releases and news articles](#) by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center and the Met Office on recent decadal predictions, which included ASPECT results. Furthermore, a [blog post](#) was published by the Met Office on “Seamless decision-making for climate adaptation”, as well as an [article](#) from a Spanish business school interviewing Albert Soret, the project coordinator, and an interview of coordinator Marta Terrado in [Alter](#).

3.8.2 Webinar series

A series of webinars will be organised in ASPECT, targeting the different sectors tackled in the project. These aim to encourage discussions among participants such as on scaling-up project prototypes, and to build capacity within the different user communities.

The first webinar took place in December 2025, and focused on the wine and agriculture sector (read more [here](#)). Titled “*Climate information for the wine sector: from seasons to years ahead*”, the webinar had a total of 38 attendees.

The session explored the challenges that the changing climate poses on the wine sector and how climate predictions can help in its adaptation. The ASPECT case study on the wine sector was explored, including the prototype and indicators co-developed in the project. The webinar ended with an interactive discussion with participants.

Among the speakers were ASPECT researchers, as well as Antonio Graça from the Sogrape winery and the Scientific-Technical committee from the International Organisation of Vine and Wine, who gave a keynote speech, and a representative from Codorniu, one of the ASPECT Super Users. A key aim of the webinar was also to promote the survey conducted by WP5, which was made available a few weeks earlier.

Figure 15. (Top) Agenda of first ASPECT webinar in December 2025. (Bottom) Part of the presentation by Veronica Torralba from BSC during the webinar.

4 Website

A website (<https://www.aspect-project.eu/>) has been developed for the ASPECT project, which is an important base where project information, updates, publications and communication materials are collected. The website targets all project audiences, with diverse backgrounds.

A key component of the website is the news section, where articles offer relevant updates of the latest project events and developments.

The website provides a dynamic and constantly evolving environment, a space that changes as the project activities grow and is adapted to provide the best visibility for the different activities. Additionally, it has a visually appealing and user-friendly design, with a responsive layout that can adapt to different screen sizes. The website is optimised for search engines, ensuring that it is easily discoverable by interested parties. The site development took place during M1 and is continuously updated according to user needs. A legacy version of the website will be available for 5 years beyond the project's end.

4.1 Layout

In its current version, the ASPECT website is organised into five sections plus the homepage. These include the following:

- **Homepage:** this highlights the vision and mission of the project, and includes the latest information on project news and activities.
- **Project:** this section provides information on the project and its research, objectives and partners.
- **Get involved:** this includes information on the User Forums and Super Users. Additional sections are added as needed, for example a section on the Super User competition for recruiting two additional users (WP4), as well as information on the survey conducted by WP5, and later removed when the tasks were completed.
- **Resources:** this section compiles all relevant project resources, including scientific publications, public deliverables, and communication and dissemination material generated by the project (e.g. videos, paper briefings, infosheets).
- **News & Events:** here, articles on project news are published, as well as a list of events organised by ASPECT, or in which partners participate.
- **Contact:** this page includes information to get in touch with the project.

Additionally, links to the project’s social media channels (top right), a link to join the mailing list (banner at the bottom of pages), and the project funding information (footer) are available throughout the website.

The News & Events section is the most dynamic part of the website. Here, updates on the project activities and events are collated. These sections are populated as ASPECT activities develop during the project, to keep track of all activities related to the project or in which the project is involved, including news on User Forums, Super Users, project research (e.g. publications of interest to the general public), and conference / event participation, among others. In the page dedicated to the events, the users can find more information about the project upcoming and past events, such as webinars, workshops and conferences, as well as some relevant climate services events.

Further information on the different sections and their design can also be found in the first version of the CDEP (Deliverable 6.1).

Figure 16. Part of the home page of ASPECT project, with brief information on the project and menus of different sections appearing in the top bar.

4.2 Analytics

Between the release of the first version (January 2023, M1) and November 2025 (M35), there have been about 2,900 visits to the project website (*KPI: >500 visits - target reached*), with more than 18,300 page views and an average visit time of almost 2 minutes and 40”.

Visitors were mainly from the UK (1,500 visits), Spain (1,350 visits), Italy (1,290 visits), USA (1,137 visits) and Germany (642 visits).

Figure 17. (Top) Progression of visitors to website. (Bottom) Map images showing the countries from which users have visited the ASPECT website. More than 80% of total visits were from European countries.

The top five visited pages included the following:

- Home page - 4,739 *unique views*
- “About” page: 1,295
- “News” page: 342
- “Partners” page: 736

Direct Entries

Direct traffic dominates with nearly 6,000 visits and strong engagement.

Search Engines

Search engines are the second-largest source, bringing 1,867 visits with solid engagement. Bounce levels remain moderate, indicating good discoverability and multi-page navigation.

Website Referrals

Referrals drive 605 visits with medium engagement and manageable bounce rates, reflecting a healthy ecosystem of external sites sending interested users.

Social Networks

Social traffic contributes 408 visits with lighter engagement.

5 Social media strategy

Social media channels are valuable platforms to reach a wide community, increase visibility, and raise awareness. Presence on social media provides an opportunity for the project to reach new members of the target audiences. The scientific community and relevant research projects are also active on social media, meaning it can also be a useful platform to reach these groups. Further to this, policy audiences and other target stakeholders can also be reached through social media via less technical, engaging content.

Four social media channels are being used to engage with the project's target audiences (identified in Section 2): X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, YouTube, and Bluesky (added in November 2024 to ensure continued engagement with audiences who migrated away from X when Twitter changed ownership). Social media activities are planned internally, and all project partners encouraged to follow and engage with ASPECT's social media, sharing information about news, events, and other content covered by the project.

The current total audience across the project's social media accounts is 875 as of November 2025 (KPI target: 600 followers).

At the end of the project lifetime, the social media activity will cease. The accounts will remain available for a further year to allow content to be accessed but a message will be posted to explain the project has ended and that the accounts are not monitored. As much content as possible will be hosted on the project website to facilitate a legacy for at least 4 years from the project end.

5.1 X (formerly Twitter) and Bluesky

5.1.1 Strategy

The ASPECT X and Bluesky accounts aim to share news, results and key messages from the project. The X page can be found using the handle [@ASPECT_project](#), and the Bluesky page can be found using the handle [@aspect-project.bsky.social](#) and both are signposted from the project website and presentations.

The accounts are mainly maintained by the Met Office, with contributions by the BSC and other project partners, who are responsible for supporting the preparation of new content. The target audiences for X and Bluesky include the scientific community, public and private organisations and businesses, related research projects, the media and the engaged general public.

The content published on the project's X and Bluesky accounts includes the following:

- upcoming events organised by the project, or events in which ASPECT partners are participating
- project news, such as updates on the project activities, material and publications, all of which will be featured on the project website
- research findings synthesised into accessible outputs (such as infographics) for a non-technical audience
- links to reports, info sheets, paper briefings and other material prepared in ASPECT
- videos summarising key messages or concepts from ASPECT research
- opportunities to collaborate with the project, such as calls for evidence, opportunities to participate in user forums and webinars, and links to complete project surveys

- latest news related to climate adaptation (e.g. related to the IPCC, State of the Climate etc.)
- relevant research findings or events from other relevant research projects or organisations

The aim is to post at least 1-2 times per week, including original content, as well as reposting relevant content from other research projects and initiatives and ASPECT scientists. ASPECT posts do, when possible, tag other scientists, projects and organisations to maximise interactions

5.1.2 Analytics

The ASPECT **X account (formerly Twitter)** currently has 227 followers (as of December 2025). Between January 2023 and December 2025, there have been 342 posts on the ASPECT X account.

At the time of the previous deliverable (D7.2), the Twitter account had received a total of 45,400 impressions and 2,732 engagements with over 400 URL clicks on posts that included links. Since the change from Twitter to 'X', access to these analytics has changed and is no longer available with our current account; regardless, the KPIs for the social media accounts had already been reached at the time of publishing the previous deliverable.

The ASPECT **Bluesky account** was established in November 2024, so this is relatively new and followers have been slow to grow. So far, this account has received a total of 93 followers and has 78 posts, with 82 engagements (58 likes, 1 reply, 21 reposts and 2 quotes).

The social media engagement and reach is expected to continue growing over the lifetime of the project. The post with the most engagement so far can be found in Figure 18. A screenshot of the BlueSky and X posts Figure 18. It was a post advertising a recent interview with eminent climate scientist Professor Ed Hawkins, timed to coincide with #ShowYourStripes day and posted on 20 June 2025. This demonstrates the success that comes from targeted engagement and carefully planned content across platforms (with the post shared on LinkedIn, X, and Bluesky, the article posted on the website, the post timed to coincide with a major hashtag on a specific date, and the videos posted on ASPECT's YouTube channels).

Figure 18. A screenshot of the BlueSky and X posts.

5.2 LinkedIn

5.2.1 Strategy

A LinkedIn public project page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/aspect-project/>) was established for ASPECT. The LinkedIn page is externally facing with the intention of sharing events and showcasing the project to external professionals such as scientists, policy makers and businesses. The specific content that is posted on the page is listed below. The aim is to post at least on a weekly basis, with all project partners responsible for supporting the preparation of new content. Project partners who use LinkedIn are encouraged to share posts to capitalise on existing networks and contacts to disseminate important project deliverables and key messages.

Content for the LinkedIn page includes:

- upcoming events organised by the project, or events in which ASPECT partners are participating
- research findings synthesised into accessible outputs (such as infographics, articles and paper briefings) for a non-technical audience
- links to reports, info sheets and other materials prepared in ASPECT
- opportunities to collaborate or input into research, such as calls for evidence or opportunities to participate in surveys, webinars, and user forums

5.2.2 Analytics

The ASPECT LinkedIn page currently has 551 followers (as of December 2025), which has steadily grown from the 134 followers recorded at the time of the previous CDE deliverable (June 2024). The ASPECT LinkedIn account was established at the beginning of the project and has progressively built a following.

In the past one year (as analytics for LinkedIn are accessible only for the latest year), there have been 95 posts on the ASPECT LinkedIn account. The account received 27,250 impressions, 554 reactions, and 27 reposts in this period. The social media engagement and reach is expected to continue to grow over the remainder of the project.

5.3 YouTube

5.3.1 Strategy

A YouTube channel (@ASPECT_project, https://www.youtube.com/@ASPECT_project) was set up for ASPECT to host videos that summarise key research, outcomes and messages from the project as well as recordings of events. The videos provide valuable and engaging content for sharing on social media, as well as material for training and presentations. The primary audience for the video content are stakeholders who are external to the project but likely to be interested in the outputs, such as decision makers in government, businesses and the third sector.

Six short bespoke videos will be produced for the project. Two videos have been produced, one is in development, and the other three are being planned. Videos will be named to maximise

discoverability and engagement. The YouTube channel also hosts recordings of events such as webinars and user forums to allow participants to refer back to information or stakeholders to engage if they were unable to attend events. Videos of longer recordings will be divided into chapters to enable users to easily navigate to the relevant content. Playlists have been created for related videos, for example, for the User Forum recordings.

Currently, there are 10 uploads on the ASPECT YouTube channel (including recordings from user forums, the two official project videos, and the video interview with Ed Hawkins), these have accrued a total of 637 views.

6 Visual identity

The ASPECT visual identity was created by a user experience expert at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center, aiming to establish a recognisable and coherent ‘brand’ for the project that will be used in all project material. The design took into account basic accessibility requirements, such as selecting a colour-blind friendly palette, and the integration of elements that conveyed the ‘seamless’ concept (lines and dots). The visual identity pack includes the project logo, a colour palette, typefaces, and templates for various support materials, such as presentations and deliverables. Logos, templates and the visual identity guide are available in the ASPECT internal repository.

Figure 19. Project logo, for both white and dark backgrounds.

Figure 20. Colour palette used in ASPECT.

7 Exploitation

The purpose of exploitation is to enable the long-term impact and legacy of the developments and products that are generated by the ASPECT project. The exploitation activities aim to facilitate the use of ASPECT data, methods, and learnings in research and activities further to those covered by the project.

An internal workshop with ASPECT work package leads and wider consortium members was held in November 2025. This was designed to invite contributions and build consensus on the key focuses for exploitation, given the results of the project so far. Insights from this meeting have informed the development of a detailed exploitation overview with targeted engagement plans for three specific audiences to guide our activities for the project's final year. Additional meetings with work package leads will ensure input from all work packages to the exploitation activities and enable continued involvement from project experts in the planning of events and materials.

We plan to target **three main audience groups** for maximising the impact of exploitation activities in the final year of the project. For each audience, we have refined a clear objective and the desired audience benefit.

1. National meteorological services

- Objective: Enable NMSs to explore pathways for future forecast products informed by ASPECT findings and share learnings from working with users.
- Audience Benefit: Gain insight into emerging methods (temporal merging, downscaling) and user engagement learnings to inform service development.

2. Climate aggregators and practitioners

- Objective: Share enduring co-production learnings and good practice for using climate information across timescales. This engagement aims to scale the findings related to working with Super Users.
- Audience benefit: Access practical guidance and tools for integrating seasonal to decadal climate information into decision-making and approaching co-production processes.

3. Climate science research community

- Objective: Share key scientific research advances from ASPECT to stimulate further research.
- Audience benefit: Gain synthesised insights and methodological understanding for advancing progress towards seamless climate information and user engagement research.

Planned engagement activities include delivering a short briefing at an in-person EUMetNet meeting and a follow-up online workshop with national meteorological services; delivering a training event using examples of handling ASPECT data for the aggregator and practitioner audience; and leveraging conference presentations and side events to present syntheses on ASPECT's major advancements in temporal merging and spatial downscaling to the scientific research community to inspire further research.

Exploitation will also be a key focus at the 2026 ASPECT General Assembly which will be held in Reading, UK, in February 2026. There will be a session on exploitation aimed at all attendees,

and we are looking to organise a potential exploitation-focused event with users from multiple different sectors on the final afternoon.

As the project nears its end, ensuring the legacy of ASPECT results becomes increasingly important. Therefore we aim to utilise future communication materials such as policy briefings, videos, and infographics yet to be developed to make them targeted, practical, and audience-specific, so that they support our exploitation aims. The digital handbook is also an important resource intended to aid exploitation activities.

7.1 Digital handbook

The digital handbook, whose beta version will be available for internal review by December 2025, will provide a structured, user-centred environment to support stakeholders in understanding and applying ASPECT’s seamless climate predictions. Building on naming options under discussion (e.g., *Beyond-ASPECT*, *InsideASPECT*, *Predicting Change*), the handbook translates scientific outputs “from science to action” for non-technical audiences in policy, business, and civil society. The design is coordinated by WP7, with scientific content, data, applications, and case studies provided by WP1, WP4, WP5, and WP6.

The handbook introduces ASPECT, its objectives, and target users, followed by insights from WP5 on organisational climate risks, information needs, planning horizons, and barriers to using climate data, illustrated with clear graphs and visuals. WP1 contributes short videos explaining the scientific foundations of climate predictions, including initialization, prediction types and time scales, combining techniques, and downscaling methods. WP6 provides infographics outlining the production chain, from identifying user needs and selecting data to bias correction, multi-timescale integration, prototype development, and user testing.

Figure 21. Two different screenshots of the beta version of the ASPECT handbook.

Applications and data tools developed by ASPECT, such as the Codorníu Shiny App, ERA Explorer, story-map components, and Jupyter notebooks, demonstrate how climate information can be applied in practice. WP4 case studies showcase Super Users addressing operational challenges, following a narrative structure: organisational challenge → ASPECT solution → results, supported by visualisations, video, and quotes. Simple example plots, such as frost-risk visualisations, include guidance on interpretation, while links to the ASPECT Data Hub encourage further exploration.

By integrating multimedia, interactive resources, and narrative-driven content, the handbook offers a coherent platform that makes climate information actionable, supports knowledge transfer, and facilitates uptake of ASPECT tools for real-world adaptation planning.

7.2 The uptake of scientific advances

The uptake of new scientific developments from ASPECT, including data, novel methodologies and learning, by other scientists and ongoing projects in climate prediction and adaptation is fundamental to the long-term impact of the project and seeding of future developments. Scientific publications are a key route to this, where there has already been success with 12 peer-reviewed journal articles published so far, alongside active collaboration during the project lifetime. A key component of the scientific exploitation strategy is the nominated 'champions' for key initiatives (including CORDEX, Destination Earth and EU-missions). The champions have developed a strong awareness of ASPECT research with these important leadership initiatives and will continue to strengthen links between the projects.

7.3 Supporting user training

A user training event, organised in collaboration with WP5 and other WPs, will deliver training on the use of the delivery system developed in the project. The design, pitching and delivery of the user training event will be tailored to the user needs and will draw on the learnings from activity 7.5 and the ongoing user engagement in WPs 4 and 5. The primary aim of this activity is to ensure that key users are confident in using the data delivery system and supporting materials. It is anticipated that this activity will fall towards the end of the project when such systems and materials are available.

7.4 Targeted engagement

WP7 will support the final component of scaling up the outputs of ASPECT by aiming to increase the uptake of ASPECT data sets and advances through focused engagement with several key users of climate information. Engagement will draw on the already established ASPECT community of practice alongside targeted engagement with additional national meteorological services (NMS). Several of these institutions are considered as partners or as part of the project's external international advisory board, and the aim is to work closely with up to 10 additional national services or organisations across Europe to embed the ASPECT outputs into their service and to learn from them to improve the delivery system. The additional NMSs will be selected to achieve an optimal geographical coverage and complement the Super Users and user communities in WPs 4 and 5. The upcoming engagement with RCOFs will provide an opportunity to spark interest in the project and build relationships with new NMS.

8 Internal communication and interactions across the project

To ensure interactions among the different project partners and WPs, a number of communication channels have been established. These are detailed below.

8.1 Mailing lists

Mailing lists have been established for each WP to regularly communicate among project partners. To avoid communication overload for members not directly involved, each work package has its own mailing list, used for internal communication and organisation. All members of the ASPECT consortium have the opportunity to choose which mailing lists they would like to

be included on, this has allowed partners to be included in relevant communications which strengthens internal interactions.

8.2 Project wiki

ASPECT partners all have access to an internal online wiki website. The wiki is a repository for project material and information including project documents, branded templates, information on reporting, partner contact details and a risk register. The wiki also includes information on how to acknowledge the project in the publication or communication of results (including the EU emblem, sentence with the grant agreement number).

8.2.1 Reporting and monitoring the impact of CDE activities

On the project wiki there is a dedicated CDE page with a link to a table for reporting events, activities or outputs that ASPECT organise, participate in or produce. The reporting table captures ASPECT presentations at events, scientific publications, activities and materials produced, user engagement, proposed events and clustering activities. This information will help to assess the ongoing level of engagement and outputs from ASPECT partners and enable the progress towards impact and the respective KPIs to be monitored.

8.3 Meetings

In ASPECT we have several meeting series established to facilitate collaborative working and join up across the project. Virtual WP meetings are held on a monthly basis, where partners design, execute, track, and assess the activities planned in their WPs and the CDEP. Representatives from other WPs attend other WP monthly meetings where possible to facilitate effective collaboration and regular interactions across the project. Bi-monthly progress meetings with the project management board track overall project progress. There are additional meetings held by the user engagement committee to prepare project activities for building the communities of practice. In addition, to obtain an overview of the advances of different WPs and upcoming activities, on-demand meetings are held on a needs basis.

Furthermore, although not originally planned at the proposal stage, internal webinars are organised by WP7 as needed, where partners present their latest developments and engage in discussion with the consortium. This enhances knowledge exchange and interaction between the different WPs.

9 Evaluation and risks

9.1 Impact evaluation and CDEP updates

As we are currently in M36 of the project, the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities have advanced significantly since the first and second CDEP releases. The different activities and their status are being closely monitored on a regular basis to ensure the progress is on track. Updates on the KPIs and impact of the activities are discussed throughout the CDEP in the corresponding sections. It should be noted that the KPIs of most of the activities have either already been achieved or are on good track to achieve early on in the project.

In November 2026, a final impact evaluation and communication plan of project legacy will be published (Deliverable 7.6).

9.2 Potential barriers and risks

The potential barriers or risks to success of ASPECT CDE have been listed in Table 3. The potential likelihood and severity have been considered with proportionate mitigation measures proposed. The risks identified are being monitored and updated (if needed) to reflect the current project status.

Table 3. Risks identified, related to CDE. High (H), Moderate (M) and Low (L) likelihood and severity are assigned to each risk.

Risk or barrier	Likelihood and severity (H/M/L)	Proposed risk-mitigation measures and status
Barriers to impact may occur if ASPECT encounters difficulties in engaging stakeholders and recruiting users, or users who do engage show reluctance to embrace new methods.	Likelihood: L Severity: H	ASPECT is aware of the need to build relationships and trust with users through the project lifetime, while limiting the risk of ‘stakeholder fatigue’. The activities so far have focused on building relationships with the project Super Users, as well as a larger pool of potential users of climate information, ensuring a wider reach. Successful engagement has been achieved, as seen by the large number of participants in User Forums and the large number of applications for new Super Users. We’ve learned in the project that engagement activities benefit from a flexible approach, therefore we will likely incorporate additional engagement activities to keep the momentum between User Forums and keep the community of interest engaged.
Barriers to collaboration may occur if results are insufficiently relevant, or if there is a lack of credible routes to key initiatives.	Likelihood: L Severity: H	ASPECT’s approach of engaging with key initiatives through embedded champions will help to initiate and maintain key links and enable us to maintain a two-way dialogue to ensure shared objectives are reached.
Upsurge in COVID infections requiring lockdown	Likelihood: L Severity: L	This is no longer considered an active risk. In the case of future pandemics, all partners are now experienced at working under local lockdown and limited travel situations, with protocols improving over the past few years. These protocols can be reintroduced as needed.
Scientific barriers in the research	Likelihood: L Severity: L	Identifying scientific barriers as we answer research questions is a normal part of research and will inform future use of climate information. For those aspects most relevant for informing future adaptation, we will deploy various methods to address such barriers. For instance, we will examine several ways to merge information across time-scales and have multiple downscaling methods. Research also builds on established models and theories, and we have experienced researchers leading WPs.